

Stakeholder Communication on Destination Branding through Three Destination Axes in the Musi River Tourism Area, South Sumatra, Indonesia

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Abstract

Background: Governance, corporation, society, and complexity are fascinating subjects in research on sustainable tourism, as well as development in river areas. Therefore, this study is based on the argument that destination branding is a promise to stakeholders. Elaboration of the perspective of communication relations between stakeholders needs to be built based on the phase of coming together in managing tourism destinations.

Objective: This study aims to elaborate on the communication relationship that develops through phases of coming together to strengthen ideas and commitments to implement each stakeholder's expectations.

Method: A qualitative methodology, case study approach, was applied. The sampling technique was purposive sampling, and eight people were deliberately selected to be interviewed in a semi-structured, in-depth manner and observed. Data analysis used the Miles, Huberman, and Saldana Interactive Model.

Results: The study's results show that stakeholder involvement in destination branding involves integrated Performance and interaction between actors from the initiation, experimentation, intensification, integration, and bonding stages. For actors, collaboration, interaction, and integration can produce ideas, thoughts, and meanings that culminate in decisions to support the interests of city tourism, represented by the three axes of leading destinations.

Conclusion: Three principal destination axes in Palembang City, South Sumatra, have been built through collaborative communication between stakeholders based on the phase of coming together to initiate development, experimentation, intensive communication, and integration of cooperation, strengthening the commitment to realising the ideas, concepts, discourses, and activities offered. The government, society, and corporations carry out relational communication through their respective roles and responsibilities, with interpersonal communication between top leaders, between groups, and in teams and dynamic organisations.

Unique Contribution: The concept of bringing stakeholders together through relational communication in branding historical heritage destinations along rivers.

Recommendation: Future research can focus on maintaining stakeholder communication by including academics with different perspectives on using cultural heritage sites and heritage as commercialised destinations. Perspective of influence and perception in communication co-orientation is required.

Keyword: stakeholder communication; relational developmental; historical heritage; tourism river

Introduction

River areas are one of the resources that can be developed for tourism. It is very reasonable because rivers have the potential to narrate the journey of the place through historical relics, such as forts, bridges, and even deltas in the middle of the river. These are tourist attractions that promise memories of heritage, cultural experiences, and the river's natural beauty. When tourism develops a space rich in cultural heritage, it will naturally be intertwined with the evolution of life along the river and the growth of the river tourism destination itself. According to Masrurun & Nastiti (2023), the growth of river tourism destinations involves many stakeholders.

The growth of river tourism destinations is a continuing process involving many stakeholders, including local governments, tourism actors, local communities, and environmental organisations. Close collaboration between stakeholders is essential to ensure sustainable and balanced management of tourism areas. In addition, innovation is needed in the development of tourism activities, such as river ecosystem education packages, and local culture must be involved to strengthen the area's identity. Through tourism, stakeholder involvement is a builder of good adaptation, innovation, and collaboration. On the other hand, in the context of this research on building communication relationships, there are three institutions, namely the City Government, companies, and communities, that play a role in developing the sustainability of the three axes of tourist destinations.

However, due to poor institutional structures or mismanagement, most community-based tourism projects ultimately do not benefit the community. In stakeholder collaboration, dialogue, cooperation, and collaboration between the various stakeholders is a middle ground between the interested parties. Indonesia has several tourist destinations related to history and rivers, one of which is in the southern part of Sumatra Island. Palembang is the capital of South Sumatra, with

the Musi River as a source of life, including tourist destinations around it. Referring to Apriani (2021), the city government plans to create a leading water tourism centre there. Although the government promotes the three destinations, communication and stakeholder relationships are required. Therefore, this study aims to see how communication relations develop by strengthening ideas and commitments to meet each stakeholder's expectations.

As a formal institution, the Palembang City Government, through the Tourism Office, establishes relations with companies and the community as stakeholders. The seriousness of stakeholders is needed to implement collaborative elements to develop the three destination axes in the Musi River Area. The government has promoted the popularity of Benteng Kuto Besak (Benteng BKB), Ampera Bridge, and Kemaro Island as leading tourist destinations in Palembang City. It is a promise that must be kept to stakeholders in accordance with the Charming Palembang branding logo and tagline. Effective collaboration will produce a win-win solution.

Apart from the developmental model's theoretical significance and concept, building collaborative relationships is relevant to interactive tourism communication involving government, companies, and communities. The emphasis on the importance of understanding stakeholder collaboration, supported by Knapp's relationship-building model, has not been empirically explored in the domain of tourism communication or destination branding in the context of communication actors. The framework adopted from the Knapp Development begins by identifying the relationship development stage as the first phase, the coming together. It does not include a separate phase for this case. Stakeholder collaboration only identifies and explores relationships built on shared goals. So, to discuss the gap, this study aims to identify how communication relationships develop through the phases of strengthening ideas and commitments in implementing what is expected by each stakeholder through a form of togetherness in collaborative communication of stakeholders built for managing tourism destinations.

Literature Review

Stakeholder Collaboration

According to Farsari's (2023) and KC et al.'s (2024) view, the relationship between stakeholders will depend on the people who control these resources and their interactions. As stated by Patricia et al. (2019) Patricia et al. (2019) and Sathiyah and Tomaselli (2024), stakeholders play a key role in the destination; each stakeholder has their interests, wishes, expectations and favourites. However, there is still a lack of recognition of the important role of rivers in tourism, including the participation of local stakeholders and the economic benefits generated for the community.

Collaboration in tourism is highly dependent on the togetherness built by destination stakeholders. The study revealed that community participation and collaboration among tourism stakeholders are key to promoting sustainable tourism planning and destination development. Effective stakeholder engagement requires a range of approaches, including consultation, collaboration, and partnership, as stated by Bhatta and Josh (2023), Chiwawa and Wissink (2023) and Bozdaglar (2023).

In several previous studies, national researchers who conducted studies on tourism in Palembang and Musi River cities revealed that stakeholders are needed for tourist destinations. Collaboration

in developing three-axis destinations involves various parties working together to increase tourism potential, preserve culture, and develop infrastructure in the Musi River areas. Based on research by Hermawanto and Nurlia (2021), Herawati et al. (2022), and Darmanto et al. (2024), the government's attention to the existence of sustainable tourism is a potential that continues to develop, so that it is considered to be able to improve the community's economy in supporting the development sector.

The Coming Together Phase Concept

Building and maintaining relationships refers to the challenges of tourism communication and maximising stakeholders. The goal is to reach a consensus on developing destination branding. The process begins with raising knowledge about developing partnerships among key actors to encourage tourist interest in Palembang City. Communication with stakeholders serves as a conduit for the Palembang City Government to perceive destination branding as a viable type of promotion. Aside from meeting tourism and local community goals, it can also better meet life expectations on a larger scale. Togetherness-oriented and collaborative stakeholders will keep relationships strong enough to overcome conflicts of interest. Other relationship development models focus on how relationships develop through stages determined by specific communication behaviours that can be mapped.

The author adopted the coming together phase of the Knapp Development Model by Knapp (1978) because this model functions as a basis for studying, analysing, and providing a comprehensive framework for understanding the dynamics of relationships between each stakeholder. This study also describes the stages that individuals usually go through in their relationships and the emergence of insight into the complexity of interaction, communication, and emotional development. It helps researchers identify and navigate the various stages of relationship development, anticipate challenges, and foster healthy, dynamic, and meaningful relationships between stakeholders. Other relationship development models focus on how relationships develop through stages that are determined by specific communication behaviours that can be mapped. Other relationship development models focus on how relationships develop through stages determined by specific communication behaviours that can be mapped.

The novelty in the context of this research is that the application of the Knapp Development Model is not based solely on interpersonal communication between two individuals. However, the interpersonal relationship in question is communication between individuals in the government and individuals who represent stakeholders. These individuals communicate interpersonally on behalf of the government, companies, and society, still using a social interaction approach even though they come from groups and organisations.

Method

Research Design

This study employs a qualitative methodology and uses a case study approach. Case studies are intended to describe the development of communication relations between stakeholders in tourism development in three destination axes: Kuto Besak Fort, Ampera Bridge, and Kemaro Island in supporting destination branding, Charming Palembang. In tourism studies, case study research can

be viewed through the background of each tourist location, which is often different due to various factors, including culture, location, history, and level of development.

Sampling and Data Collection

This study used purposive sampling to select participants with relevant characteristics or experiences. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with eight key informants selected from the following member-checking criteria.

1. Involvement of city government actors in promoting historical entity-based tourist destinations;
2. Involvement of corporate actors in community empowerment;
3. Involvement of community actors in supporting government programs and management to sustain historical and cultural heritage tourist destinations.

Data collection was carried out by observing and documenting conditions in the Kuto Besak Fortress Tourism Area, Ampera Bridge, and Kemaro Island from March to April 2024. The target population of this study includes the main stakeholders who are directly involved in the management of three leading tourist destinations based on historical, cultural heritage and community empowerment.

Table 1: Respondent profile

Respondent	The main area of work	Criteria
The local government, as well as the Palembang City Tourism Office	Tourism destination promotion regulation.	1
Vice President of Social and Environmental Responsibility Department of PT Pupuk Sriwidjadja, Palembang	Initiated the idea of the Partnership and Community Development Program based on community empowerment.	2
Local community around the Kemaro Island and the Toa Pekong Buddhist Foundation management	Implementation of government programs and management of tourist destinations in river areas.	3

Meanwhile, the observation method is used, using a non-participatory approach to obtain a comprehensive picture of stakeholder involvement in three tourist destinations and activities at the Benteng Kuto Besak destination: Ampera Bridge and tourist attractions, such as Temples, Pagodas and Cap Go Meh celebrations, Kampung Aer, floating net cage ecotourism, floating farmers, and Floating Restaurants in Kemaro Island.

Data Analysis

Data acquisition results are stored as a reference for reporting existing conditions after stakeholder communication and collaboration. Data analysis techniques are applied to the Miles and Huberman Interactive Model through three stages.

Table 2: Interactive model data analysis

Stages	Implementation
Reduction data	The organisation of information involves actors in their respective roles, interests, and forms of communication applied.
Display data	Data on the experiences of actors involved in a particular and relevant destination are then compiled into a table that shows the relationship between stakeholder roles and the coming together phases carried out.
Conclusion and verification	This conclusion is verified by comparing or triangulating data from various sources to ensure its validity. The actors involved realise the coming together based on collaborative initiatives, experiments in relationships, intensive or regular communication, integration of interests and cohesive unity to work together between actors.

Results

This study aims to show the phase of coming together based on roles, interests and forms of communication. The results of the study found that the phase of coming together of stakeholders includes the initiation phase of collaboration that is motivated by each actor's role, experimentation in relationships, intensive or regular communication, integration between interests and cohesive unity to work together between actors.

Roles, interests and communication channels of stakeholders

The role of stakeholder involvement

The government has several regulatory and collaborative roles as a policy maker with various related stakeholders. The local government and the Palembang City Tourism Office formulate policies through the Strategic Plan, which involves a structured approach to defining goals, strategies, and actions for an organisation or region over a specific period, typically five years.

"The goal, strategies, and actions process begins with identifying the long-term vision and mission of the organisation or region. It sets the foundation for all subsequent planning. The government promotes tourism products involving strategies to make the tourist attraction widely known, attractive, and accessible to potential visitors" (Government informant, SA, 3/2024).

This is a major component of tourism marketing: Informing potential tourists about a destination or attraction's existence and unique features. PT Pupuk Sriwidjadja (PT Pusri) Palembang is a company engaged in producing and distributing fertilisers that also collaborates with the Palembang City government.

"Collaboration with corporations and external government parties is carried out for promotional purposes. The city's Tourism Office has promotional media for the Palembang 360 Program Digital promotion, radio podcasts and Instagram Charming Palembang" (Government informant, ME, 3/2024).

This collaboration is through a CSR forum, specifically in the Social and Environmental Responsibility department, which includes various initiatives to support the agricultural sector and community welfare in the city.

“CSR programs that focus on the environment and community help empower and create sustainable positive impacts, such as those carried out in the Kampung Aer community, Kemaro Island” (Corporation informant, DA, 3/2024).

The resident and Tri Dharma Foundation, the manager of the Hok Tjing Bio/Rio temple and pagoda, manages tourist destinations with historical, cultural and religious backgrounds on Kemaro Island.

Stakeholder interests

The issue of interest in advancing Palembang City tourism is related to the implementation of tourism affairs, and the development of the tourism sector is how it can affect the economic, social, and environmental sectors. Palembang City has a tourist area that can be used as a potential opportunity for the tourism sector itself, in addition to the cultural potential that can be used as a selling point for tourism offered to tourists.

"Referring to the latest strategic plan, we have 15 leading tours. It comes from 77 destinations, various natural, historical and cultural tourism, as well as artificial tourism, including Kuto Besak Fort, Ampera Bridge and Kemaro Island" (Government informant, SA, 3/2024).

Corporations have a strategic interest in establishing close partnerships with the Palembang City Government in implementing social responsibility (Corporate Social Responsibility-CSR) through a healthy and prosperous program with an exit strategy of providing maximum benefits and independence to residents through ecotourism driven by residents through corporate development.

“Actually, the policy is because there is Social and Environmental Responsibility (TJSL) in Pusri itself. We do have a program related to community development” (Corporation informant, AD, 3/2024).

Meanwhile, the management of the Toa Pekong Buddha Foundation is interested in promoting pilgrimage tourism to temples and pagodas and maintaining the tradition of annual celebrations.

Communication channels

Stakeholder actors communicate issues of interest regarding the three axes of tourism destinations using the perspective of working relations and strategic communication. Destination using the perspective of working relationships and strategic communication. It is demonstrated by the successful collaboration of the city government's tourism office. Communication that begins with good relationships or closeness, such as with the Tourism Agency, is greatly influenced by a combination of long-established interpersonal communication and maintained official communication.

"We can do it through meetings. We can do it through deliberations. We can do it through the presentation of our programs. So uniting the vision and mission. Do not let it be wrong later on that we are at odds. What we want is not the same as their vision and mission" (Government Informant, SA, 3/2024).

Official correspondence communication preceded by informal communication can be interpreted as an initial step to inform new developments or initiatives, such as for the promotion and launch of the Sesera Pusri Floating Restaurant.

"For the one in tourism, it is because of us, yes, the term is good relations, working together to celebrate Chinese New Year/Chinese New Year and the Cap Go Meh tradition" (Community Informant, KAP, 3/2024).

"Some community activities supported by the Palembang City Tourism Office. Usually send letters, always written, face-to-face communication is possible" (Community Informant, VAL, 2024).

Formal communication, such as letters, is chosen to ensure transparency and official documentation. It creates a balance between flexibility and professionalism.

Relational Development: The Coming Together Phase

Phase 1. Initiation of stakeholder roles and involvement

Initiation is the initial step to start a relationship by stating the program and the purpose of the implementation and integration of the objectives and commitments of the government to corporations and communities in the three destination axes. Government communication relations are built to promote historical, religious, cultural and river tourism destinations. The government approaches the interests of the managers of the temple tourism destination on Kemaro Island as a priority destination by implementing the Chinese New Year celebration and the Cap Go Meh tradition as the peak celebration and the end of the Chinese New Year, which falls on the 15th night. This tradition involves various activities such as lantern festivals, lion and dragon performances, and prayer rituals at the monastery facilitated by the Toa Pekong Foundation. The community and temple managers on Kemaro Island support the determination of Kuto Besak Fort, Ampera Bridge and Kemaro Island as historical and cultural heritage tourism destinations. PT Pusri, as a corporation, determines Kemaro Island as the location for the CSR program, with the ecotourism exit program as an alternative destination on Kemaro Island. The communication channels applied are interpersonal between top leaders or community leaders.

Phase 2: Experimenting

The government experimented relations through an approach to the leaders of PT Pusri, the community and managers of temples and pagodas on Kemaro Island by being involved in maintaining historical and cultural heritage through three destinations located in the Musi River area. PT Pusri, as a corporation, has prepared a community empowerment program through floating net cages, floating farming, and organising the establishment of a floating restaurant in the waters of the Musi River located in Kampung Aer, Kemaro Island. The Toa Pekong Foundation is responsible for public activities and good relations by opening access to Kemaro Island for

visitors, pilgrims, tourists and stakeholders. This action is considered a declaration of maintaining history, cultural heritage and the nobility of places of worship, culture and the history of the entry of acculturation of Chinese culture with the local population of Palembang.

Phase 3: Intensifying

The frequency of communication with stakeholders is carried out intensively, both formally and informally, especially in communicating the implementation of government promotion programs. Representatives of residents or community leaders participate in various activities and share orientations with residents. PT Pusri consolidates the perception and vision of social empowerment (CSR) through the Social and Environmental Responsibility Forum program, Palembang. The Toa Pekong Foundation periodically conveys its policies regarding places of worship, pilgrimage/tourism sites and anniversary celebrations.

Phase 4: Integrating

Integration helps ensure that tourism develops sustainably, taking into account economic, social and environmental aspects. Collaboration between government, corporations, and communities produces more innovative tourism products and services, which are of higher quality and in line with the needs of tourists and local communities. The government agrees to use funds and assistance from the company's CSR and involves individuals in the Tourism Awareness Group. Corporations agree to cooperate and implement government programs and empowerment from companies. The community agrees to build a pagoda to help improve facilities for the Kemaro Island destination. The Toa Pekong Foundation is pleased to provide routine attractions and performances every year, such as the Chinese New Year celebration and the Cap Go Meh tradition.

Phase 5: Bonding

All stakeholders show commitment to supporting activities until the completion of ideas and concepts in the form of promotional activities programmed by the Tourism Office. The tourism awareness group is committed to supporting destination development. The government is committed to including Chinese New Year and Cap Go Meh celebration activities in the 10 Calendar of Charming Events Palembang every year, routinely and prioritised. PT Pusri is committed to implementing community empowerment programs to improve the quality of life of residents, sharing information, and promoting empowerment products, namely floating restaurants, as an exit strategy for the Healthy and Prosperous program for residents.

Table 3: The relationship between stakeholder roles and the coming together phases

Phase	City Government	Community		Corporation (CSR)	Forms of Communication
	Tourism Office <i>(regulator & collaborator)</i>	Resident <i>(participant)</i>	Tourist destination manager <i>(host)</i>		
Initiating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communicate policies, integrate government 	Accepting government policies and participating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supporting government programs for the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing Kuto Besak Fortress and Ampera 	Interpersonal relationships between top leaders

	<p>objectives and commitment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stakeholder interest approach. ▪ Destination development financing. 	<p>in operational and cultural participation.</p>	<p>sustainability of historical and cultural heritage tourism destinations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Statement of maintaining the values of Buddhist Tridharma worship and historical and cultural tourism. 	<p>Bridge as historical and cultural heritage tourism destinations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establishing Kemaro Island as a historical, religious and ecotourism destination through corporate involvement through CSR and Toa Pekong Foundation, Palembang. 	
Experimenting	<p>Approaches with community leaders and residents to engage in joint activities to further assess compatibility and build rapport.</p>	<p>Building relationships by participating in activities from the sub-district/district office, the Tourism Office and related offices.</p>	<p>The declaration is responsible for public activities and good relations by opening access for visitors, pilgrims and stakeholders in maintaining history, cultural heritage and the nobility of places of worship, culture and the history of the entry of acculturation of Chinese</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Planning charity and community development programs. ▪ Managing social, economic and environmental-based CSR programs with an ecotourism exit strategy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Interpersonal or groups ▪ Interpersonal in team ▪ Dynamic organisational

			citizens with local Palembang residents.		
Intensifying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Communicating the implementation of the Company's programs. ▪ Determining individual involvement in the Tourism Awareness Groups. 	Representatives of residents or community leaders closely follow various activities and share orientations with residents.	The Tridharma Toa Pekong Foundation regularly conveys its policies regarding places of worship, pilgrimage/tourism locations and anniversary celebrations.	Consolidating programs through the Palembang Social Responsibility (CSR) Forum and between stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Interpersonal or groups ▪ Interpersonal in team Dynamic organisational
Integrating	Agreeing on the implementation of the use of company CSR funds and assistance.	Agreeing on cooperation and implementing government programs and empowerment from companies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreeing on the construction of temples and pagodas. • Provision of regular attractions and shows. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Helping to repair facilities. ▪ Sharing information and promoting activities. ▪ Involving volunteer services. 	Organisational
Bonding	Commitment to supporting activities until the completion of ideas and concepts in the form of activity promotion.	Tourism awareness groups are committed to supporting destination development by providing formal certificates.	Commitment to include Chinese New Year and Cap Go Meh celebration activities in the Calender of Charming Event.	Commitment to implementing community empowerment programs to the stage of improving the quality of life of residents.	Organisational

Discussion

The Tourism Office maximises its duties and functions in improving the quality and diversity of its citizens' economy by empowering resources and partners in the tourism sector. The relationship between the government and corporations is based on a sense of generosity and social and

environmental responsibility. The relationship began with a common interest in improving the quality of life of the people of Kemaro Island through community empowerment programs. Based on the development stage of the relationship between the City Tourism Office and the community and companies through the initial five stages of the Knapp Relational Development Model, it shows that the city government plays the role of a regulator, corporations are interested in realising the exit program of community empowerment programs and routine religious celebrations and priority destinations of Kemaro Island by the Tridharma Foundation community so that they are always included in the 10 Top Calendar of Charming Events Palembang shows that there are many interests of the stakeholders involved.

On the other hand, other challenges arise: companies play a relatively larger role in the trial, integration, and bonding stages because they have CSR funds. However, at the intensification stage, the local government plays a role as a bridge for implementing ideas reflected in the destination branding with the tagline "Charming Palembang". The stage of assisting corporate relations in a program may end, but as a stakeholder who guides the Kampung Air community, Kemaro Island, PT Pusri, as a corporation, remains bound. As for the management of destinations such as the Toa Pekong Foundation, the owner of the Hok Tjing Bio temple and pagoda, as well as annual celebration tourist attractions such as Chinese New Year and Cap Go Meh, their communication relations remain intact as long as the Tourism Office includes these tourist attractions in the 10 Top Event Calendar of Charming Event Palembang with a mutual agreement. Likewise, relationship development is carried out by the Government and the Foundation periodically, both interpersonally and formally.

At the local community level, the government strengthens relations through the role of the Tourism Awareness Group in each RT/RW. Maintaining communication relationships tends to stagnate until the validity period of the Decree on the appointment of the Tourism Awareness Group from the Tourism Office as the administrator of the Tourism Awareness Group ends. The City Government's homework is to strengthen governance and government functions further to support and form collaborative patterns in developing sustainable and competitive tourism, both with corporations and communities, as well as academics/universities and press institutions as stated by Bhatta & Josh (2023), Chiwawa and Wissink (2023), and Bozdoglar (2023).

Conclusion

Stakeholder collaboration in the three-axis destination of historical and cultural heritage destinations in the Musi River area was built through the coming together phase. The process that was gone through started from the initiation of relationship building, relationship experimentation, intensive communication, and integration of cooperation, strengthening the commitment to realising ideas, concepts, discourses, and activities offered through the three-axes destinations, namely Kuto Besak Fort, Ampera Bridge and the beauty of Kemaro Island. Stakeholder relationship communication was built within the framework of social and environmental responsibility, demonstrated by the actor's communication approach, both formal and informal, and in the dynamics of the organisation through the issues of each interest.

Suggestions for Future Research

Future research is focused on the perspectives of influence and perception of co-orientation communication between stakeholders, including historians, academics, cultural heritage activists, and press institutions with government interests in marketing historical tourism destinations without disturbing their historical status.

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